

1 *Article*

2 **Update on the conservation status of Townsend's Shearwater (*Puffinus***
3 ***auricularis*): distribution of breeding colonies, reproductive success**
4 **and population trends under various conservation scenarios**

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20 **Abstract** Townsend's Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) is a critically endangered seabird. Its
21 distribution is restricted to the Pacific Ocean and ranges from Mexico to Central America. Nearly 20
22 years ago, the breeding population of Townsend's Shearwater, which is endemic to the Revillagigedo
23 Archipelago in Mexico, was estimated to consist of fewer than 100 breeding pairs. Since then,
24 conservation initiatives, including eradicating invasive mammals, have been implemented in the
25 archipelago. We assessed the current status of Townsend's Shearwater by mapping the distribution
26 of breeding colonies, estimating breeding population size, evaluating reproductive success,
27 describing ongoing threats and modelling population trends under different conservation scenarios.
28 From 2016 to 2024, we conducted field surveys on the islands of Socorro and Clarión using acoustic
29 monitoring techniques in historical nesting areas. We estimated that the breeding population of
30 Townsend's Shearwater on Socorro consists of fewer than 200 pairs and documented the return of a
31 small breeding population to Clarión after a 30-year absence. However, notable reproductive failure
32 persists due to native predators such as land crabs, snakes and ravens. Indeed, the population has
33 exhibited a slow decline driven by interactions between native and invasive species. Without ongoing
34 restoration efforts, including the removal of feral sheep and cats, the population will likely face
35 extinction. To ensure the survival of Townsend's Shearwater, it is crucial to implement innovative
36 management actions to improve reproductive success.

37

38 **Keywords** bird conservation, breeding biology, invasive species, Mexico, Revillagigedo
39 Archipelago, species management, threatened species, Townsend's Shearwater

40 **Introduction**

41 Seabirds are the most threatened bird group worldwide due to human-induced threats, including
42 invasive species at nesting sites, fisheries bycatch, climate change impacts and infectious diseases
43 (Dias et al., 2019; FAO, 2024). Indeed, 56% of seabird species are experiencing population declines,
44 with 43% listed as Threatened and 5% listed as Critically Endangered on the Red List of the
45 International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (Phillips et al., 2022). In Mexico, 25% of the
46 seabird species found within the country are listed on the IUCN Red List (IUCN, 2024). This is
47 particularly concerning, as Mexico currently ranks third globally in terms of seabird diversity and
48 second in terms of the number of endemic seabird species that breed within its territory (Croxall et
49 al., 2012). At present, 21% of seabird species are protected under Mexican law, including Townsend's
50 Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) (Berlanga et al. 2008).

51 Townsend's Shearwater is listed as Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List (BirdLife
52 International, 2018). Although Townsend's Shearwater is an endemic breeder of the Revillagigedo
53 Archipelago in Mexico (BirdLife International, 2018), its distribution, which is restricted to the
54 Pacific Ocean, ranges from Mexico to Central America (Ainley et al., 2020). In Mexico, Townsend's
55 Shearwater has historically used the islands of Socorro, San Benedicto and Clarión as breeding sites
56 (Anthony, 1898; Hanna, 1926). Like other seabird species, Townsend's Shearwater is subject to
57 several anthropogenic and natural threats that have decimated its breeding sites and resulted in
58 population declines and the extirpation of multiple seabird colonies in the region (Wolf et al., 2006;
59 Bedolla-Guzmán et al., 2019).

60 The introduction of sheep (*Ovis aries*) in 1869 (Brattstrom, 2015) to Socorro resulted in a loss of
61 breeding habitat that persisted for over 100 years (Ortiz-Alcaraz et al., 2016). In addition, human
62 settlements on Socorro, which were first established in 1957, have resulted in the introduction of
63 invasive predators such as cats (*Felis catus*) and house mice (*Mus musculus*; Jehl & Parkes, 1982).
64 In San Benedicto, volcanic eruptions that occurred in 1952 and 1953 extirpated the breeding
65 population (Brattstrom & Howell, 1956). In recent decades, individuals have occasionally been
66 reported near San Benedicto (Pitman & Ballance 2002), but the reestablishment of a Townsend's
67 Shearwater colony on the island has not been confirmed. In Clarión, introduced species, such as sheep
68 (*Ovis aries*), pigs (*Sus scrofa*), rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) and chickens (*Gallus gallus*), have
69 deleteriously affected the ecosystem, with feral pigs causing the extirpation of Townsend's
70 Shearwater by the 1980s (Santaella & Sada, 1991).

71 Accurately estimating the breeding population size of Townsend's Shearwater is challenging due to
72 the inaccessibility of nesting colonies and the lack of systematic surveys, resulting in variable
73 estimates over the years, ranging from tens to thousands of pairs. Using 15 years of pelagic survey
74 data (1980–1994), the average global breeding population was estimated to consist of 10,600 pairs
75 (Spear et al., 1995). In 1981, the first quantitative estimate conducted on Socorro suggested that the
76 breeding population consisted of 1,000 pairs (Jehl, 1982). Later on, Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen
77 (2004) added the maximum counts of 1993 and 1997 and estimated the breeding population on
78 Socorro to consist of 550 pairs. These authors also predicted a rapid decline in the breeding population
79 due to the presence of feral cats while reporting no evidence of nesting activity on Clarión (Martínez-
80 Gómez & Jacobsen, 2004). Notably, the recent estimates of a global population of 200–999
81 individuals (Birdlife International, 2018) and 75 breeding pairs on Socorro indicate a severe decline
82 in abundance (Martínez-Gómez et al., 2015). The status of Townsend's Shearwater on San Benedicto
83 remains unknown due to the complexity to access the island to conduct surveys.

84 In response to the threats posed by invasive species, invasive mammals have been removed from
85 numerous seabird-islands over the past 25 years (Aguirre-Muñoz et al., 2018), allowing some seabird
86 populations to recover (Méndez Sánchez et al., 2022). *Grupo de Ecología y Conservación de Islas*
87 (GECI), in coordination with the Mexican federal government, eradicated pigs from Clarión in 2002
88 (Aguirre-Muñoz et al., 2018) and sheep from Socorro in 2012 (Ortíz-Alcaraz et al., 2016). In 2014,
89 GECI began to eradicate cats on Socorro (Ortíz-Alcaraz et al., 2017). These actions have allowed the
90 recovery of vegetation (Ortíz-Alcaraz et al., 2016) and increased the abundance of landbirds and
91 reptiles on the island (Ortíz-Alcaraz et al. 2017). While some populations of flora and fauna have
92 recovered, the status of the Townsend's Shearwater population has not been assessed.

93 To update the current status of Townsend's Shearwater on Socorro and Clarión, we conducted the
94 first systematic monitoring (2016–2024) of its remaining breeding populations. In particular, this
95 study aimed to 1) map the current distribution of breeding colonies, 2) estimate breeding population
96 size, 3) evaluate reproductive success, 4) model population trends under different conservation
97 scenarios, 5) identify current threats at breeding sites and 6) propose novel conservation and
98 restoration actions. The results of this study will be essential for guiding future conservation actions
99 for this critically endangered species.

100 **[Study area]**

101 Fieldwork was conducted on the islands of Socorro and Clarión during the breeding season
102 (November to June, occasionally extending to mid-July) from 2016 to 2024. These islands are located

103 over 300 km from mainland Mexico in the Eastern Tropical Pacific and form part of the Revillagigedo
104 Archipelago National Park (Fig. 1; SEMARNAT–CONANP, 2019), also a World Heritage Site. The
105 California Current and North Equatorial Current systems converge in the region, creating conditions
106 that support high biodiversity (SEMARNAT–CONANP, 2019). At present, 12 pelagic seabird
107 species breed in the region, including Townsend’s Shearwater (SEMARNAT et al., 2015).

108 Socorro (13,039 ha) is the largest island in the Revillagigedo Archipelago and has an elevation of
109 1,050 m.a.s.l. at its highest point (SEMARNAT–CONANP, 2019). Two climate zones are present on
110 Socorro, namely a semiarid zone (0–400 m.a.s.l.) and a subtropical zone (400–1050 m.a.s.l.), and the
111 average temperature of the island ranges from 19.7–11.2 °C (SEMARNAT–CONANP, 2019).
112 Potential native predators for Townsend’s Shearwater adults and chicks on Socorro include the Red-
113 tailed Hawk (*Buteo jamaicensis socorroensis*) and the land crab (*Johngarthia oceanica*) (Whetje et
114 al. 1993, GECI unpublished data).

115 Clarión is the second largest island (1,925 ha) in the Revillagigedo Archipelago and has an elevation
116 of 320 m.a.s.l. (CONANP, 2017). The island hosts grasslands, scrublands and coastal vegetation,
117 including 58 species of xerophilous plants (CONANP, 2017). A large fire in 1984 and the introduction
118 of mammals have severely modified the vegetation of the island (Everett, 1988). Potential native
119 predators for Townsend’s Shearwater on Clarión include the endemic Clarión raven (*Corvus corax*
120 *clarionensis*) and the Clarión snake (*Masticophis anthonyi*) (McLelland, 1926, CONANP, 2017).

121

122 **Methods**

123 *Distribution of breeding colonies*

124 To determine the current distribution of Townsend’s Shearwater colonies on Socorro and Clarión, we
125 conducted auditory surveys, acoustic surveys, and burrow searches. Auditory surveys were performed
126 from November to April (2016–2023) on new moon days at dusk (19:00 to 21:00 h) and, occasionally,
127 at dawn (03:30 to 05:30 h). At each site, we recorded the number of calls, call direction, and
128 approximate distance and whether the birds emitted calls in flight or from the ground (Raine et al.,
129 2017). Survey sites were selected based on historical records (Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen, 2004),
130 mapped, and analysed to identify potential nest areas for subsequent burrow searches.

131 Acoustic surveys were conducted from November to April (2019–2023). All call counts were
132 recorded with Song Meter (SM2, SM3 and SM4) Acoustic Recorders (Wildlife Acoustics Inc.,
133 Maynard, USA). On Socorro, acoustic recorders were deployed over a historical nesting area of

134 1,819.43 ha (600 m.a.s.l.) (Jehl, 1982). The acoustic recorders were deployed every 300 m to avoid
135 double counting (Raine et al., 2017) with two recording schedules: 1) 10 min on and 20 min off (2019-
136 2022) and 2) 1 min on and 5 min off (2022-2023). Recorders operated from 19:00 to 05:30 h,
137 independent of the moon phase. The recording mode was mono, with a sampling rate of 24-92 KHz,
138 gain of 16.0 dB and Preamp of 26 dB. On Clarión, the acoustic recorders (SM4) were deployed every
139 500 m using the same recording program and specifications as those deployed on Socorro.

140 Burrow searches were conducted from November to February and from June to July (2016–2023) in
141 sites with historic records of burrows, high nocturnal activity, circling birds or ground calls. Field
142 personnel conducted exhaustive searches and were sometimes accompanied by wildlife detection
143 dogs (pointers and shepherds) (Grymm-Seyfarth et al., 2021). The dogs were trained to passively
144 detect targets by remaining static to avoid damaging burrows or birds. Search tracks were recorded
145 using handheld GPS or GPS mounted on dog collars.

146 *Reproductive success*

147 We used infrared Trophy Cam HD trail cameras (Bushnell Corporation, Overland Park, USA) to
148 record data on burrow status (active or inactive), activity, predation events and fledgling success. The
149 cameras operated in night mode and were checked every 15 days, and additional cameras were
150 installed in nest colonies to identify cat presence. We checked for predation signs between camera
151 checks.

152 We visually assessed burrow occupancy (Eq. 1) by the presence of feathers, guano, and cleanliness
153 and by confirm burrow visits in photographs:

$$154 \quad \text{Occupancy} = \frac{\text{Number of active burrows}}{\text{Total number of burrows}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

155 Nest content was examined with a borescope (NTS 300 [8-mm lens, Teslong Technology, New York,
156 USA) to confirm the presence of adults, eggs, or chicks. The burrows were checked once a week, and
157 the reproductive metrics of clutch size, hatching success (proportion of eggs that hatch), fledgling
158 success (proportion of chicks that fledge), reproductive success (proportion of eggs that result in
159 fledglings) and reproductive rate (proportion of pairs breeding) were calculated. The seasons of 2016
160 and 2017 were omitted from the analysis due to the lack of borescope data. In 2019 and 2020, the
161 borescope failed, and breeding signs (e.g., eggshells, down remains and chick carcasses) were used
162 to determine the number of breeders. Reproductive success was estimated considering only confirmed
163 breeders. We included the breeding success results of one occupied artificial burrow from 2019 to
164 2023 and two of these burrows in 2024.

165 *Population size and dynamic model*

166 We used call rates as a proxy of burrow density (Oppel et al., 2014; Hart et al., 2021). Four fixed
167 recorders were deployed at sites with known burrow abundance from November to May (2017–2024).
168 Recorders operated under the first schedule and specifications previously described. Population size
169 was projected with a Leslie matrix (Leslie, 1945; Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen, 2004) using three
170 scenarios: 1) current (chick predation by land crabs and no cat predation), 2) worst-case (no
171 management interventions and high predation by cats) and 3) optimal management (reduced chick
172 predation and a moderate increase in reproductive success). Population and reproductive parameters
173 were estimated from monitoring data (2018–2023) (Table 1); survival probability (for each age class
174 [1–6 years]) and the cat predation rate were taken from Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen (2004).

175 *Data analysis*

176 We manually reviewed recordings (Hart et al., 2021) using Raven Pro v. 1.5 (Cornell Lab of
177 Ornithology) and counted all Townsend’s Shearwater calls that were visible in spectrograms. Calls
178 that were obscured or overlapped were counted by listening to the recording. Recordings that
179 contained calls that were highly obscured by heavy rains or strong winds were excluded. Townsend’s
180 Shearwater calls were classified as broad-band information with low fundamentals (<1.4 kHz) and
181 harmonics reaching 4 kHz (Baptista & Martínez-Gómez, 2002). The duration of each call was ~5 s;
182 spectrograms longer than 5 s were considered more than one call (e.g., 10 s = 2 calls). Townsend’s
183 Shearwater presence or absence and the number of calls per site were plotted and classified by natural
184 breaks in QGIS. Pictures and videos from camera traps were reviewed manually to confirm the
185 presence or absence of birds, fledglings or predators.

186 We estimated breeding population size from the call rates in a sample consisting of the three darkest
187 days of each month in each nesting area with a known number of burrows. An average call rate from
188 all recorders was calculated for each year (2019–2021). The density of burrows and call rates from
189 the known nesting areas on Socorro were used to estimate the number of burrows in the area
190 (including sites without calls) (Fig. 2). Through a linear equation, we estimated the total number of
191 breeding pairs (N_{breeding}).

192 The total population size (N_{total} ; number of pairs) was calculated from the number of breeding pairs
193 (N_{breeding}) and the breeding proportion (r_{breeding}) of the population with Eq. (2):

194
$$N_{\text{total}} = \frac{N_{\text{breeding}}}{r_{\text{breeding}}} . \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

195 The proportion of breeding pairs was calculated with Eq. (3):

196
$$r_{breeding} = r_{mature} \times \rho_{breeding} , \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

197 where r_{mature} is the proportion of sexually mature individuals in the population and $\rho_{breeding}$ is the
198 breeding probability of a mature individual (i.e., 0.55), which was calculated with data from 2016–
199 2023. The number of non-breeding pairs ($N_{non-breeding}$) was calculated from the total population
200 size and the proportion of non-breeding pairs according to Eq. (4):

201
$$N_{non-breeding} = N_{total} \times r_{non-breeding} . \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

202 The proportion of non-breeding pairs ($r_{non-breeding}$) was calculated with Eq. (5):

203
$$r_{non-breeding} = r_{mature} \times \rho_{non-breeding} , \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

204 where $\rho_{non-breeding} = 1 - \rho_{breeding}$ is the non-breeding probability of a mature individual. Lastly,
205 the number of sexually immature pairs ($N_{immature}$) was calculated from the total population size and
206 the number of mature non-breeding and breeding pairs with Eq. (6):

207
$$N_{immature} = N_{total} - (N_{breeding} + N_{non-breeding}) . \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

208

209 **Results**

210 *Distribution of breeding colonies*

211 On Socorro Island, we recorded Townsend’s Shearwater calls in 87 (47%) of the 183 surveyed sites
212 (Fig. 2). Of these, 29 (16%) high-potential nesting sites within ~400 ha (22%) of the surveyed area
213 and 3% of the surface area of the island were identified. The other sites were considered to be flyway
214 paths for shearwaters entering or exiting the island. Through burrow searches, we covered ~145 ha
215 (36%) of the potential nesting area and identified 27 active burrows above 800 m.a.s.l. that were
216 distributed in small colonies consisting of 2–9 burrows. Some isolated burrows were found at sites
217 without calls or with few recorded calls. Eight burrows were occupied by new pairs (i.e., pairs that
218 were not identified in previous surveys or pairs occupying newly dug burrows). In 2023, a potential
219 colony was identified through acoustic recordings in the north-eastern area of the island at an altitude
220 of 600 m.a.s.l., although no active burrows were recorded.

221 On Clarión, we identified a breeding pair at the *Cerro Gallego* site in 2016. Four new burrows were
222 found from 2017 to 2019. By 2020, we had surveyed 95% of the island with acoustic recorders and
223 identified nine sites with calls and two sites with active burrows (Fig. 3). Calls were located in the
224 eastern portion of the island in the *La Mujer Dormida* site and in the northern portion of the island in

225 the *Cerro Gallego* site. Active burrows ($n = 5$) were found only on rocky substrates with sparse or no
226 vegetation.

227 *Reproductive success*

228 Reproductive success on Socorro varied among years (average of 43% [0–63%]). No fledglings were
229 detected in 2018, and only one fledgling from an artificial burrow was detected in 2019 (Table 1).
230 The average burrow occupancy was 92% (76–100%), and the average reproductive rate was 59%
231 (31–82%). All except two pairs were confirmed to be breeders at least once. Most breeding pairs
232 (79%) produced a fledgling at least once, whereas only 28% succeeded in producing fledglings more
233 than once in consecutive years; 21% never produced fledglings. Breeding success in artificial burrows
234 (100% hatching success, 66.6% fledgling success) was higher than in natural burrows over six
235 consecutive years. However, in 2024, a new nesting pair in an artificial burrow failed to hatch a chick.
236 Failures in reproductive success occurred due to different factors. Land crabs predated 24.3% of
237 chicks, which was visually confirmed by direct observations or chick remains in nests (Plate 1).
238 Although crab attacks on fledglings and adults were recorded, crab predation occurred only with
239 chicks aged 20 days or younger. In addition, 16.2% of chicks disappeared without evidence, although
240 these disappearances coincided with increased crab activity. In 2020 and 2024, the failure of two
241 chicks to fledge in an artificial burrow coincided with the presence of land crabs inside the nest
242 chamber. In 2022, we found evidence of land crabs consuming a broken egg. Notably, we did not
243 find any evidence of cat predation. Egg failures were due to disappearances (21.6%) and hatching
244 failure (2.7%), as well as broken (2.7%), non-viable (2.7%) or abandoned eggs (2.7%). In addition,
245 27% of egg or chick losses could not be explained because the failure occurred between the incubation
246 and hatching stages.

247 On Clarión, average burrow occupancy was 81%. Reproductive success was not estimated due to the
248 depth and complexity of the burrows. However, egg laying at the entrance of a burrow was recorded
249 on video in 2019. Auditory surveys and camera traps confirmed breeding attempts in three burrows,
250 but no fledglings were recorded. Photographic evidence showed frequent visits by Clarión snakes
251 (Plate 2) and land crabs, which are potential predators of eggs and chicks. Raven visits were less
252 frequent.

253 *Population size and dynamic model*

254 The Townsend's Shearwater breeding population on Socorro Island was estimated to be 175 pairs
255 (90%, CI = 94–386 pairs). Considering all other non-breeders and young birds at sea, the global

256 population was estimated to be 481 pairs (962 individuals). The breeding population on Clarión was
257 not estimated due to insufficient data. However, with the available data from field observations and
258 surveys, we conservatively estimated that no more than 10 breeding pairs inhabit the island.

259 The total population of Socorro, including breeders, non-breeders and young birds, was modelled
260 according to the current scenario, which indicated that the population will continue to decline at a
261 rate of 1% over the next 15 years. The worst-case scenario model, which included high predation by
262 cats, indicated that without management actions, the breeding population would decrease by 63%
263 over the next 15 years. The optimal management model predicted a 30% increase in population size
264 over the next 15 years (Fig. 4), considering a conservative increase of 0.14 in breeding success (60%)
265 by reducing chick predation.

266 **Discussion**

267 *Distribution of breeding colonies*

268 We confirmed the presence of Townsend's Shearwater breeding colonies at high elevations (800
269 m.a.s.l.) on Socorro. However, no evidence of colonies was found in the southern portion of the
270 island, although a few scattered burrows were present to the north-west of Mount Evermann, which
271 differs from previous records (Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen, 2004). The calling activity and presence
272 of feather and faeces indicated that the Townsend's Shearwater has recovered some of its historical
273 nesting areas (Wehtje et al., 1993) on Socorro.

274 In Clarión, we confirmed active burrows in the two highest points of the island known as *Cerro el*
275 *Gallego* and *La Mujer Dormida* in the western and eastern areas of the island, respectively. However,
276 we found no evidence of colonies in sandy soil under grasslands, as reported by Anthony (1900) and
277 Hanna (1926). Instead, Townsend's Shearwater burrows were confined to rocky areas above 200
278 m.a.s.l. The absence of colonies under grasslands may have been due to ravens, which dig into sandy
279 burrows to access chicks and eggs (Hayward et al. 2015). In addition, competition with invasive
280 rabbits for habitat (Ávila-Guerrero et al., 2016) may have also resulted in the notable absence of
281 colonies. Lastly, habitat destruction and predation by invasive pigs (Howell & Webb 1989), as well
282 as a fire in 1984 (Everett 1988), may have also negatively affected Townsend's Shearwater nesting
283 habitat.

284 *Reproductive success*

285 Reproductive success in Socorro was highly variable between years and lower (59%) than that of
286 similar species like Newell's Shearwater (*Puffinus newelli*) (66%, Ainley et al., 2001), Manx

287 Shearwater (*Puffinus puffinus*) (62–75%, Lee et al., 2023) and Wedge-Tailed Shearwater (*Ardenna*
288 *pacifica*) (68.5%, Hyrenbach & Hester, 2022), but similar to that of the Black-Vented Shearwater
289 (*Puffinus opisthomelas*) (36%) during El Niño conditions and subject to predation (Keitt, et al., 2003).
290 The reproductive failures of Townsend’s Shearwater in 2018, 2019, 2021 and 2024 coincided with
291 the transitions from La Niña to neutral and neutral to El Niño conditions (National Weather Service
292 NOAA). Under neutral and El Niño conditions, sea surface temperatures, the frequency of tropical
293 storms (CONANP 2017), humidity and, consequently, land crab activity increase (Pérez-Chi, 2005),
294 which may have been responsible for high chick predation. In Clarión, no Townsend’s Shearwater
295 fledglings were recorded during the study period. Based on video data, the main predators of chicks
296 are likely snakes, which have been documented predated Laysan Albatross (*Phoebastria*
297 *immutabilis*) chicks on the island (Wanless et al., 2009).

298 *Population size and dynamic model*

299 Our population estimate for Socorro (175 pairs) is more optimistic than the previous estimate of ~75
300 pairs of Martínez-Gómez et al. (2015). However, the current scenario model predicted a sustained
301 population decline despite managing invasive mammals and increasing the availability of breeding
302 habitat on Socorro. This suggests that native predators, particularly land crabs, hinder population
303 recovery. Notably, the impacts of land crabs on seabirds have been documented in other regions, such
304 as Cayo Ratón in Puerto Rico, where loss of Roseate Terns (*Sterna dougallii*) chicks was likely due
305 to predation by a land crab (*Gecarcinus ruricola*; Shealer & Burger, 1992). Similarly, on Malpelo
306 Island in Colombia, another land crab (*Johngarthia malpilensis*) was found to predate Nazca Booby
307 (*Sula granti*) eggs and chicks (López-Victoria & Werding, 2008).

308 Indeed, Kaeding (1905) suggested that crabs may have prevented nesting on Socorro by predated on
309 birds. In contrast, thousands of shearwaters were found nesting on San Benedicto where very few
310 crabs were observed (Anthony, 1900). Hanna (1926) did not suggest any relation, but noted low land
311 crab abundance and bigger shearwater nesting colonies on Clarión. Thus, Townsend’s Shearwater
312 breeding populations on Clarión and San Benedicto may have been historically larger (Anthony,
313 1989) than on Socorro due to predation and the poor suitability of available habitat. Importantly, the
314 estimates of breeding population size reported for Socorro by previous authors (Jehl, 1982; Whetje
315 et al., 1993; Martínez-Gómez & Jacobsen, 2004) may have been overestimated due to the inclusion
316 of immigrants from remnant populations on San Benedicto and Clarión, where nesting habitats were
317 lost (Santaella & Sada, 1991), or due to shearwater behaviour that led to double counting (e.g., flying
318 in circles while arriving to colonies (Griesemer and Holmes 2011).

319 On Clarión, human activities and invasive rabbits have increased food availability for native ravens
320 and snakes (Ávila-Guerrero et al., 2016). Rabbits, which serve as prey for snakes, inhibit the recovery
321 of vegetation, including cactus (*Opuntia* sp.; Brattstrom, 2015), a food item for ravens. Thus, the
322 reduction in the availability of *Opuntia* sp. has been found to indirectly probably increase seabird
323 predation by ravens (Ávila-Guerrero et al., 2016). Indeed, the decline of the Townsend's Shearwater
324 population is likely the result of synergistic effects due to habitat loss and hyperpredation (Spatz et
325 al., 2023a).

326 *Conservation implications and future research needs*

327 All management actions for Townsend's Shearwater must be accompanied by monitoring programs
328 (Raine et al. 2020), with particular attention paid to the behaviours and responses of predators to
329 management actions. Importantly, while cat eradication is concluded, cat incursions can be managed
330 by a permanent field team and by controlling invasive mammals throughout the breeding season.
331 While progress in cat removal has reduced the extinction risk of Townsend's Shearwater (Croll et al.
332 2021), breeding success remains low due to predation by native predators, necessitating further
333 action.

334 Increasing breeding success by mitigating chick predation is critical to preventing extinction. The
335 optimal management model highlighted the importance of increasing fledgling and breeding success
336 to boost the population size of Townsend's Shearwater. To this end, social attraction techniques have
337 proven to be an effective tool. Indeed, these techniques have resulted in a positive response (79%)
338 when implemented with 49 procellariids species (Schreiber and Burger, 2002).

339 On Clarión, key future restoration actions should include establishing artificial colonies within a
340 predator-proof fence to protect chicks from rabbits, snakes, and land crabs. Additional actions should
341 include eradicating rabbits, appropriately managing human garbage which provides food for ravens,
342 and restoring grasslands where shearwaters historically nested. On Socorro, fully eradicating cats
343 from the island and preventing chick predation by land crabs are critical to improving breeding
344 success.

345 Although nest boxes limit the risk of predation by land crabs, their designs must be improved to fully
346 exclude these predators. In addition, translocating chicks to safer breeding areas may improve
347 breeding success. In the Hawaiian Islands, this action has successfully improved the breeding success
348 of Newell's Shearwater (Young & VanderWerf, 2024). Thus, this action, which would result in
349 establishing new colonies in protected areas, could produce the same outcomes on Socorro and
350 Clarión.

351 If chicks are translocated on Socorro, then the Barn Owl (*Tyto alba*) must also be managed to ensure
352 the safety of Townsend's Shearwater fledglings (Raine et al., 2022). To this end, the ecology of the
353 Barn Owl must be understood to successfully implement management actions during key periods of
354 the Townsend's Shearwater breeding season (Raine et al., 2022). The Barn Owl has been recorded
355 on Socorro since the 1960s (Jehl & Parkes, 1982), but its potential impact on Townsend's Shearwater
356 has likely been underestimated, especially considering that Barn Owls can catch birds in mid-air away
357 from their burrows (Raine et al. 2020).

358 Lastly, further research on Townsend's Shearwater vocal behaviours is needed to improve estimates
359 of population size and dynamics (Arneill et al., 2019). In addition, post-breeding studies are needed
360 to identify potential threats at sea such as bycatch and the effects of climate change (Días et al., 2019,
361 Rodríguez et al., 2019). It must also be determined if the Townsend's Shearwater has returned to
362 breed on San Benedicto, with future studies on this island evaluating potential predation by land
363 crabs, potential competition with Wedge-Tailed Shearwater for nesting habitat (Villard et al., 2006),
364 and erosion (Brattstrom, 2015).

365

366 **Author contributions**

367 Study design: AOA, FSC; funding acquisition: FMS, AAM, AOA; fieldwork: FSC, IML, EPV, YBG,
368 AFB, AAO, JGS, NCH, BRM; data analysis: BRM, FSC; writing: FSC, YBG, AFB; revision: all
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370

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380

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382

383 **Ethical standards** This research did not involve human subjects, experimentation with animals, or
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385

386 **Data availability** The raw data supporting the findings of this study are available from the
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388

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572

573 TABLE 1 Reproductive performance of Townsend's Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) on the Socorro
 574 Island, Revillagigedo Archipelago, Colima, Mexico, during the breeding season (2016–2024).
 575 Numbers in parenthesis are breeders in artificial burrows.

Parameter	2016 n = 4	2017 n = 12	2018 n = 17	2019 ^{bc} n = 20	2020 ^c n = 21	2021 n = 21	2022 n = 24	2023 n = 28	2024 n = 29
Occupancy (%)	100	100	94	95	95	95	87	89	76
Breeding pairs	2 ^a	7 ^a	5	1(1)	9(1)	12(1)	17(1)	15(1)	11(2)
Reproductive rate (%)	ND	ND	31	ND	50	65	82	64	62
Hatching success (%)	ND	ND	ND	50	70	92	72	75	69
Fledging success (%)	100	100	0	100	86	42	69	83	55
Overall success (%)	ND	ND	0	50	60	38	50	63	38

576 ^a based on number of fledglings

577 ^b No content checks. Egg shell remains were used to estimate breeding pairs.

578

579

580 FIG. 1 Location map of the Revillagigedo Archipelago, Colima, Mexico. Acoustic surveyed areas on
581 Socorro Island (a) and Clarión Island (b) are shaded with lines.

582

583

584

585 FIG. 2 Map of acoustic recording sites on Socorro Island, Revillagigedo Archipelago, Colima,
586 Mexico. Number of calls per site and Townsend's Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) burrow locations
587 are shown in circles and squares respectively.

588

589 FIG. 3 Map of recording sites on the Clarión Island, Revillagigedo Archipelago, Colima, Mexico.
590 Number of calls per site and Townsend's Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) burrows locations are
591 shown in circles and squares respectively.

592

593 FIG. 4 Population trends of the Townsend's Shearwater in the Revillagigedo Archipelago, Mexico,

594 under different conservation scenarios.

595

596 PLATE 1 Land crab (*Jhongarthia oceanica*) predated Townsend's Shearwater chick in 2021 on
597 Socorro Island, Revillagigedo Archipelago, Colima, Mexico (Photo Credit: GEICI).

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599 PLATE 2 Clarión snake (*Masticophis anthonyi*) visiting an active burrow of the Townsend's
600 Shearwater (*Puffinus auricularis*) on Clarion Island, Revillagigedo, Mexico (Photo Credit: GECI).